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VOLUME 1

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A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“DISREGARDED SOMEBODY”

Equipping myself through education,
Not for fame, nor recognition,
But simply to be counted in,
To earn a living, to rise and begin.

Perhaps they see me as powerless,
No influence, no strong connections,
Yet I offer my life with dedication
To a calling that shapes the next generation.

While I longed to spread my wings,
To share the knowledge I've nurtured within,
I was overlooked,
Disregarded, neglected, and given less opportunity.

Still, I gather every heartache,
Turning pain into fuel, not a break.
Staying positive, grounded, and humble,
For I believe, God is the best planner of all.